

Synthesis of Substituted Chrysenes

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Syntheses of 3-ethyl-9-methylchrysene (9) and 1,3,9-trimethylchrysene (9a) are described. 2-(7'-Ethyl-1'-naphthyl)ethyl bromide (6) and 2-(5',7'-dimethyl-1'-naphthyl)ethyl bromide (6a) were condensed separately with 2-carbethoxy-5-methylcyclohexanone to afford ethyl α,α -(4-methyl-2-cyclohexanone)- γ -(7'-ethyl-1'-naphthyl)butyrate (7) and ethyl α,α -(4-methyl-2-cyclohexanone)- γ -(5',7'-dimethyl-1'-naphthyl)butyrate (7a) respectively. PPA cyclisation of 7 gave a mixture of 8 and 8b while that of 7a gave only 8a. Catalytic dehydrogenation of 8 and 8b afforded 9 and that of 8a gave 9a. The products were characterised by physical data.

Literature reports the synthesis of substituted chrysenes¹. Electrophilic substitution reaction has been used for getting chrysenes substituted at the 6 and 12 position². Photochemical oxidation of 1,6-diaryl-1,3,5-hexatrienes led to the formation of some disubstituted chrysenes³. Many other substituted chrysenes are rare and many polysubstituted chrysenes are unknown.

1-9; R₁=C₂H₅, R₂=H
1a-9a; R₁=R₂=CH₃
8b; R₁=C₂H₅, R₂=H

We describe here unambiguous synthesis of two new substituted chrysenes, 3-ethyl-9-methylchrysene

(9) and 1,3,9-trimethyl chrysene (9a). For the synthesis of 9 and 9a, 2-(7'-ethyl-1'-naphthyl)ethyl bromide (6) and 2-(5',7'-dimethyl-1'-naphthyl)ethyl bromide (6a) were prepared by the condensation of ethyl bromoacetate with 7-ethyltetralone (1) and 5,7-dimethyltetralone (1a) to give ethyl 7-ethyl-3,4-dihydronaphthyl-1-acetate (3) and ethyl 5,7-dimethyl-1-hydroxytetralin-1-acetate (2a) respectively. Dehydration of 2a gave 3a. Both 3 and 3a were heated with sulphur to get ethyl 7-ethylnaphthyl-1-acetate (4) and ethyl 5,7-dimethylnaphthyl-1-acetate (4a). Lithium aluminium hydride reduction of 4 and 4a afforded the corresponding carbinols (5 and 5a) which gave the corresponding bromides (6 and 6a) by reaction with phosphorous tribromide.

The bromo compounds (6 and 6a) were separately condensed with 2-carbethoxy-5-methylcyclohexanone to give ethyl α,α -(4-methyl-2-cyclohexanone)- γ -(7'-ethyl-1'-naphthyl)butyrate (7) and ethyl α,α -(4-methyl-2-cyclohexanone)- γ -(5',7'-dimethyl-1'-naphthyl)butyrate (7a). Both 7 and 7a gave spectral data consistent with their structures. PPA cyclisation of 7 gave only 3-methyl-9-ethyl-1,2,3,11,12,12a-hexahydrochrysene (8) (characterised by spectral data) when the reaction was carried out at 100°. When the reaction temperature was raised to 130-40° for 20 min towards the end of the reaction, it afforded 8 along with another compound 8b which showed no carbonyl absorption in its ir spectrum. Compound 8b without further purification in its pmr spectrum showed approximately two protons signal at δ 8.5 and 8.0-7.2 for five protons and signals in the region δ 3.7-2.6 for approximately six protons, consistent with its presumed structure, 3-methyl-9-ethyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrochrysene. Both the compounds 8 and 8b on aromatisation gave 3-ethyl-9-methylchrysene.

Similar cyclisation of 7a gave 3,7,9-trimethyl-12a-carbethoxy-1,2,3,11,12,12a-hexahydrochrysene (8a). Aromatisation of 8b afforded 1,3,9-trimethylchrysene (9a).

Experimental

All m.p.s. and b.p.s. are uncorrected. Spectral data were recorded at C.D.R.I., Lucknow and I.I.C.B., Calcutta.

7-Ethyltetralone (1) and 5,7-dimethyltetralone (1a) were prepared by succinylation of ethylbenzene and *m*-xylene to get the keto-acids, *p*-ethylbenzoylpropionic and 2,4-dimethylbenzoylpropionic acids respectively. Clemmensen reduction followed by intramolecular acylation with polyphosphoric acid afforded 1 and 1a in good yields. The pmr spectra of 1 and 1a were consistent with the reported⁴ ones. 1-Carboxy-4-methylcyclohexan-2-one was prepared according to a known procedure⁵.

Ethyl 7-ethyl-3,4-dihydro-1-naphthylacetate (3): A portion of the solution of 7-ethyltetralone (12 g) and ethyl bromoacetate (11 g) in a mixture of benzene and toluene (1 : 1) was added to zinc wool (5–6 g). A few crystals of iodine and a trace amount of mercuric chloride were added to the reaction mixture and warmed on a steam-bath. When a vigorous reaction started, the remaining proton of the solution was added at such a rate that it refluxed in its heat of reaction. After complete addition it was refluxed for 2 h. After the usual work up, compound 3 was collected at 185–90°/0.9–1.0 mm. After removal of the unreacted ketone as semicarbazide, it was distilled at 180–85°/0.9 mm (lit.⁶ 170–75°/7 mm) (12 g), ν_{\max} (film) 1750 (ester), 1620, 1510, 1380, 900, 840 cm^{-1} (1,2,4-trisubstituted-benzene); *m/z* 244 (M^+).

Ethyl 5,7-dimethyl-1-hydroxytetralin-1-acetate (2a): It was prepared from 5,7-dimethyltetralone (20 g) and ethyl bromoacetate (18 g) in a similar manner as described above and collected at 185–90°/1.0 mm, (13 g), ν_{\max} (film) 3520 (OH), 1750 (ester), 1620, 1400 and 1390 cm^{-1} . On heating 2a with acetic anhydride and after the usual work up it gave 3a, b.p. 145–50°/0.7–0.8 mm; ν_{\max} (film) 1750 (ester) and 1620 cm^{-1} ; *m/z* 244 (M^+).

Ethyl 7-ethyl-1-naphthylacetate (4) and *ethyl 5,7-dimethyl-1-naphthylacetate* (4a): Compounds 3 and 3a were separately heated with calculated amounts of sulphur at 200–20° for 3 h. The usual work up and chromatographic purification over alumina using petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) gave the aromatic esters; 4 (90%), 160–63°/0.3–0.4 mm (Found: C, 79.29; H, 7.54. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2$ requires: C, 79.33; H, 7.438%); ν_{\max} 1745 (ester), 1610, 1510, 1400, 880, 840, (1,2,4-trisubstituted-benzene) and 760 cm^{-1} (1,2,3-trisubstituted-benzene); 4a (87%), 165–70°/1.00 mm (Found: C, 79.35; H, 7.51. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_2$ requires: C, 79.33; H, 7.438%); ν_{\max} (film) 1740 (ester), 1635, 1610 and 1515 cm^{-1} . The esters 4 and 4a were hydrolysed to the corresponding acids and crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether as white solids. The acids of 4 and 4a melted at 134–36° and 158–60° respectively.

2-(7-Ethyl-1-naphthyl)ethanol (5) and *5,7-dimethyl derivative* (5a): To a slurry of LAH (2 g) in dry

THF (25 ml) cooled in ice-water, 4 (8.5 g) was added dropwise with stirring. It was then refluxed for 3 h and worked up in the usual manner to yield 5 (7 g), 155–60°/0.7–0.8 mm; ν_{\max} (film) 3380 cm^{-1} (OH). Similarly, 4a (8 g) gave 5a (6.5 g), b.p. 170–75°/0.7 mm; ν_{\max} (film) 3360 cm^{-1} (OH).

2-(7-Ethyl-1-naphthyl)ethyl bromide (6) and *5,7-dimethyl derivative* (6a): Phosphorous tribromide (5 g) was gradually added to 5 (6.5 g) cooled in ice. It was allowed to stand at room temperature overnight and then warmed on a steam-bath for 0.5 h. The unreacted PBr₃ was decomposed with water, extracted with ether, the ether extract successively washed with water, NaHCO₃ solution and brine till neutral, dried (Na₂SO₄) and the solvent removed to yield 6 (5.5 g), 155–60°/0.6 mm (Found: C, 63.69; H, 5.85. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{15}\text{Br}$ requires: C, 63.87; H, 5.703%). Similarly, 5a (6 g) gave 6a (5.4 g), 168–73°/0.6 mm (Found: C, 63.71; H, 5.79. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{15}\text{Br}$ requires: C, 63.87; H, 5.703%).

Ethyl α,α -(4-methyl-2-ketocyclohexane)- γ -(7'-ethyl-1'-naphthyl)butanoate (7): 1-Carboxy-4-methylcyclohexan-2-one (4 g) was gradually added to pulverised potassium (1 g) in dry xylene cooled in an ice-bath. It was left overnight when a solid cake was formed. 2-(7-Ethyl-1-naphthyl)ethyl bromide (5 g) was added and heated on an oil-bath at 120–40° for 4 h and then at 150–60° for 0.5 h. The reaction mixture was decomposed with ice-water and extracted with benzene. The benzene extract was washed with water, dried (Na₂SO₄) and the solvent removed. The fraction at 190–220°/0.8–1.0 mm was collected and subjected to chromatographic purification over silica gel using petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) as eluant to yield the product (3 g), 210–20°/0.9 mm; ν_{\max} (film) 1735 (ester), 1710 (C=O), 1600, 1505, 1455, 890, 840 (1,2,4-trisubstituted-benzene) and 760 cm^{-1} (1,2,3-trisubstituted-benzene); δ (CDCl₃), 8.04–7.2 (6H, ArH), 4.6–4.1 (2H, q, COOCH₂CH₃), 3.1–2.1 (6H, benzylic and CH₂–CO), 1.6–1.1 (13H, alicyclic, aliphatic) and 1.1–0.8 (3H, CH₃); *m/z* 366 (M^+).

Ethyl α,α -(4-methyl-2-ketocyclohexane)- γ -(5,7'-dimethyl-1'-naphthyl)butanoate (7a): It was obtained as the condensation product of 6a (5 g) with the same carboxylate under similar conditions and similar purification, (3.2 g), 225–30°/0.6 mm; ν_{\max} (film) 1745 (ester), 1720 (C=O), 1610, 1520, 1400, 875, 835 (1,2,3,5-tetrasubstituted-benzene) and 770 cm^{-1} (1,2,3-trisubstituted-benzene); δ (CDCl₃), 8.0–7.15 (5H, ArH), 4.3 (2H, q, COOCH₂CH₃), 3.4–2.2 (10H, aromatic CH₂, benzylic, CH₂–CO), 1.8–1.1 (10H) and 0.9 (3H, CH₃); *m/z* 366 (M^+).

Cyclisation of 7 and 7a. Formation of 3-methyl-9-ethyl-12a-carboxy-1,2,3,11,12,12a-hexahydrochrysene (8), *3-methyl-9-ethyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrochrysene* (8b) from 7 and *3,7,9-trimethyl-12a-carboxy-1,2,3,11,12,12a-hexahydrochrysene* (8a) from 7a: Ethyl α,α -(4-methyl-2-ketocyclohexane)- γ -(7'-ethyl-1'-naphthyl)butanoate (2.5 g) was stirred with polyphosphoric acid (P₂O₅, 18.5 g; H₃PO₄, 13 ml)

and heated on a steam-bath for 2.5 h and then at 130–40° for 20 min. Usual work up and chromatographic separation over silica gel using petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) gave two fractions. The less polar fraction (8b; 600 mg) showed no carbonyl absorption in its ir spectrum and its mass spectrum showed molecular ion peak at m/z 274; δ (CDCl₃) 8.5 (2H) and 8.0–7.2 (5H), 3.7–2.6 (6H). The more polar fraction (8; 500 mg) gave ν_{\max} (film) 1745 (ester), 1645 and 1620 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 7.9–7.1 (6H, ArH, olefinic), 4.1 (2H, q, COOCH₂-CH₃), 3.4–2.4 (5H, benzylic, allylic), 1.64–1.2 (12H) and 0.9 (3H, CH₃); m/z 348 (M^+).

Compound 7a (3 g) was stirred with polyphosphoric acid (P₂O₅, 18 g; H₃PO₄, 12 ml) on a steam-bath for 2.5 h. Its usual work up and chromatographic purification over silica gel gave a single product (8a; 2 g), b.p. 230–35°/1 mm; ν_{\max} (film) 1740 (ester), 1635 and 1615 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 8.0–7.08 (5H, ArH, olefinic), 4.18 (2H, q, COOCH₂-CH₃), 3.6–2.4 (9H, Ar-CH₃, allylic, benzylic), 1.8–1.2 (9H, alicyclic, aliphatic) and 0.9 (3H, CH₃); m/z 348 (M^+).

Dehydrogenation of 8 and 8a. Formation of 9 and 9a: The cyclised product 8 (1 g) was heated with Pd-C (0.1 g; 10%) in a sealed tube at 300–20° for 10 h. It was then extracted with ether. The residue after removal of ether was chromatographed over alumina using petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) as eluent to yield 9 as solid which was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 152–54°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3100, 3080, 3000, 2950, 2890, 1610, 1515, 1400, 1280, 1200, 1170, 900, 860 and 820 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 8.8–8.56 (4H, m, ArH), 8.14–7.8 (4H, ArH), 7.64–7.2 (2H, ArH), 3.2–2.8 (2H, q, CH₂CH₃), 2.66 (3H, s, ArCH₃), 1.6–1.36 (3H, t, CH₂CH₃); λ_{\max} (EtOH) 224 (log ϵ 4.55), 258 (4.81), 268 (4.03), 294 (4.087), 320 (4.083), 348 (3.28), 365 nm (3.29); m/z 270 (M^+). The solid formed TNB complex in ethanol as orange needles, m.p. 166–68°.

The cyclised product 8b on dehydrogenation afforded a white solid, m.p. 151–54° (crystallised from ethanol), identical with 9 obtained from dehydrogenation of 8.

The catalytic dehydrogenation 8a (1 g) with Pd-C (10%) under condition as stated above and after chromatographic purification over Al₂O₃ using petroleum-ether (b.p. 60–80°) afforded 9a as white solid which was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 164–66°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3100, 3060, 3020, 2980, 2920, 2870, 1610, 1500, 1455, 1390, 1300, 1200, 1055, 875, 860, 800 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 8.8–8.4 (4H, ArH), 8.2–7.8 (3H, ArH), 7.5–7.28 (2H, ArH), 2.76 (3H, s), 2.64 (3H, s) and 2.6 (3H, s); λ_{\max} (EtOH) 228 (log ϵ 4.38), 252 (4.063), 262 (4.087), 273 (4.188), 326 nm (3.398); m/z 270 (M^+).

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